

HIGH INTEGRATION OF RESEARCH MONOGRAPHS IN THE EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE INFRASTRUCTURE

Deliverable 7.5: Report on Task 7.4

Grant Agreement number	:	731102
Project acronym	:	HIRMEOS
Project title	:	High Integration of Research Monographs in the European Open Science infrastructure
Funding Scheme	:	EINFRA-22-2016
Project's coordinator Organization	:	CLEO-CNRS
E-mail address	:	pierre.mounier@openedition.org
Website	:	http://operas.hypotheses.org
WP and tasks contributing	:	WP7 Task 7.4
WP leader	:	UGOE
Dissemination level	:	PU
Due date	:	30 June 2019
Delivery date	:	28 June 2019

Networking and Communities Outreach within the Framework of the HIRMEOS Project

Author

Andrea Bertino (Universität Göttingen Stiftung Öffentlichen Rechts)

Contributors

Judith Schulte (Max Weber Stiftung)

Erzsébet Toth-Czifra (DARIAH-EU)

Rowan Hatherley (Ubiquity Press)

Javier Arias (Open Book Publishers)

Francesco de Virgilio (Ubiquity Press)

Table of contents

Executive Summary	1
Background	2
The Task 7.4 Alignment and Exploitation	2
General Aspects of the HIRMEOS Communication Strategy	2
Part 1: Activities, Publications and Dissemination Material	4
1.1 Conferences and Presentations	4
1.2 Workshops organized	8
1.3 Webinars	12
1.4 Peer-reviewed Papers	12
1.5 Other Publications	14
1.6 Fact-sheets	15
1.7 Other Dissemination Materials	17
1.8 Video & Hypervideo	17
1.9 Website and Social Networks	18
PART 2: Strengthening the OA Book in different Communities	22
2.1 Academic Communities	22
2.1.1 Context of the Communication Activities	22
2.1.2 Results and Perspectives	22
2.2 University Presses and Libraries	25
2.2.1 Context of the Communication Activities	25
2.2.2 Results and Perspectives	25
2.3 Funding Institutions	27
2.3.1 Context of the Communication Activities	27
2.3.2 Results and Perspectives	27
Abbreviations	28

Figures

[Figure 1: A poster frequently used during the course of the project](#)

[Figure 2: Final workshop: overall satisfaction](#)

[Figure 3: Final workshop: relevance of content](#)

[Figure 4: Final workshop: participant types](#)

[Figure 5: Conceptual map realized for the hands-on lab at the German Librarian Days 2018](#)

[Figure 6: Fact-sheet on the annotation service](#)

[Figure 7: One of the flyers developed at the beginning of the project](#)

[Figure 8: HIRMEOS website analytics \(April 2017-June 2019\)](#)

[Figure 9: HIRMEOS website visitor: most represented countries](#)

[Figure 10: Twitter last 28 days \(28 June 2019\)](#)

[Figure 11: Twitter Impressions from April 2017 to 28 June 2019](#)

[Figure 12: A tweet on our last webinar](#)

[Figure 13: OA Book realized with OBP: Online readership](#)

[Figure 14: OA Book realized with OBP: Unique visits by country](#)

Executive Summary

This document is the HIRMEOS deliverable 7.5 'Reporting on Task 7.4', i.e. fostering and strengthening communication with a network of key stakeholders and scientific communities (with special focus on fields with low Open Science uptake). It presents the results of the joint efforts of the HIRMEOS Task 7.4 members from Göttingen University (UGOE), University of Turin, DARIAH-EU, Max Weber Stiftung, EKT e-Publishing, and all the members of the consortium. The work has been led by UGOE.

The document reports about the activities of community outreach aimed to strengthen the networks of stakeholders involved in the realization, use and dissemination of Open Access Monographs. It shows how the different services and tools implemented in the course of the HIRMEOS project could contribute to increasing the interest of different communities for Open Access Books.

The document is structured as follows: **The first part** presents activities and deliverables of the WP7, focusing on the most important aspects of our community outreach and exploitation activities.

In **the second part**, the report presents the results of our strategy to strengthen the OA scholarly book in relation to three groups: the scientific community, the research libraries as providers of publishing services, and the funding institutions.

Background

The Task 7.4 Alignment and Exploitation

The Task 7.4 (led by UGOE) was charged with fostering and strengthening communication with network of key stakeholders and scientific communities (with special focus on fields with low OS uptake). In order to fulfil this task, four key activities have been planned:

- Integrate user feedback channels into HIRMEOS web portal to support alignment of technical developments with user needs
- Develop training and dissemination templates for technical WPs to support their interaction with target groups
- Develop and organise liaison activities for engagement with stakeholders and communities to align with HIRMEOS' technical developments with user needs, face-to-face and virtual (how to webinars, knowledge cafés, all hands workshops, etc.).
- Develop integration scheme (organisational, legal, technical) to allow other platforms to implement HIRMEOS services Develop benchmarking and reporting schema for successful interaction with stakeholders and communities. Foster international cooperation via endorsements and joint activities

General Aspects of the HIRMEOS Communication Strategy

The communication strategy developed by the WP7 was based on the following general insights:

- the scholarly monograph is an essential tool for the humanities and social sciences (HSS);
- this format takes advantage of its integration into the Open Science (=OS) system, i.e. of digitalization and OA;
- this integration encounters specific difficulties;
- overcoming these challenges requires more than a generic advocacy for OA publishing and OS, concrete incentives for the realization and use of OA monographs.

The incentives provided in the framework of the HIRMEOS project were technical ones, i.e. services for digital publishing platforms developed on the basis of open source tools.

Therefore, the activities of community outreach and exploitation by WP 7 focused on these technical incentives by pursuing three main lines of action:

- providing information about the services and tools implemented;

- contributing to their critical development and diversified implementation through an exchange with the various interested communities;
- promoting their use by involving users directly in various activities.

To reach a wider target audience in the field of OS, communication activities have been coordinated with the communication strategy of OPERAS, an *European Research Infrastructure for the development of open scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities*. Thus, the connection between HIRMEOS' and OPERAS' networks was exploited to improve the outreach of the communication activities and general sustainability of the project.

Part 1: Activities, Publications and Dissemination Material

1.1 Conferences and Presentations

1. Tempo di Libri – Book Fair Milan, Italy, 20 april 2017, Andrea Bertino and Pierre Mounier: Panel discussion on HIRMEOS and OA Books.
2. DARIAH-EU Annual Event, Berlin, Germany, 26-27 April, Pierre Mounier, Talk on HIRMEOS.
3. AEUP Conference, Stockholm University Library, Sweden, 16-17 May, Pierre Mounier, Talk on OPERAS.
4. Project Day, SUB Göttingen, Germany, 13 June 2017, Andrea Bertino, Poster Presentation
5. OAI10 – CERN – UNIGE Workshop on Innovations In Scholarly Communication, Geneve, Switzerland, 21-23 June 2017, Arnauld Gingold, Poster Presentation
6. Digital Humanities Benelux Conference 2017, Utrecht, Nederland, 3-5 July 2017, Andrea Bertino, Poster Presentation.
7. Open Science Fair, Athens, 6-8 September 2017, Marina Angelaki & Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou, Poster Presentation.
8. Open-Access-Tage 2017, Dresden, Germany, 11-13 September 2017, Margo Bargheer and Andrea Bertino, Talk: “Was brauchen OA Monographien?”
9. 9th Conference on Open Access Scholarly Publishing (COASP) 20-21 September 2017, Andrea Bertino, Poster Presentation.
10. MUNIN conference on scholarly publishing, 22-23 November 2017, Andrea Bertino, Poster Presentation.
11. ZBW Leibniz Information Centre for Economics, Hamburg (Germany), May 2018, Francesco de Virgilio, Talk: “Metrics and Altmetrics Service in the HIRMEOS Project”, *metrics Repository Workshop (COAR).
12. ELPUB Conference, University of Toronto, Canada, June 2018, Brian Hole, Francesco De Virgilio, Chealsye Bowley, Talk: “Shared infrastructure for next-generation books: HIRMEOS”; Elisabeth Ernst, Talk: “The Value of Network Sustainability”.
13. ELPUB Conference, University of Toronto, Canada, June 2018, Javier Arias, Talk: Collecting inclusive usage metrics for Open Access publications: The HIRMEOS Project.
14. The Digital Humanities at Oxford Summer School, 2-6 July, Oxford (England), Andrea Bertino, Poster Presentation.
15. The Digital Humanities at Oxford Summer School (DHOxSS).
16. PUBMET Conference, University of Zadar, Croatia, September 2018. Andrea Bertino, Talk: “Leveraging concept in Open Access Publications”.

17. JADH Eighth Conference of Japanese Association for Digital Humanities “Leveraging Open data”, Tokyo, Japan, 9-11 September 2018, Luco Fappiano, Poster Presentation.
18. Open-Access-Tage Graz, Austria 24-26 September 2018. Margo Bargheer, Andrea Bertino: “Chancen und Herausforderungen unterschiedlicher Geschäftsmodelle beim Publizieren von Open Access Büchern”.
19. “Die Zukunft des wissenschaftlichen Buches: Monographien in Open Access. Ein Workshop der Allianz der Wissenschaftsorganisationen”, Bonn, Wissenschaftszentrum, September 2018. Andrea Bertino, Talk: “Der Weg zur Open Access Monographie aus Sicht des Infrastrukturprojekts HIRMEOS”.
20. DI4R: “Challenges for Research Communities around Open Science”, Lisbon, Portugal, 9-11 October 2018, Luca Foppiano, Talk on entity-fishing.
21. CONFOA conference, Lisbon, Portugal, 2-4 October 2018, Marie Pellen, Talk: OPERAS: “Um modelo de infraestrutura colaborativa para as Ciências Sociais e Humanas”.
22. DARIAH_FOSTER Workshop “How to make the most of your publications? Discover evolving trends in open access”, 21 January 2019, Pierre Mounier, Talk: “Open Scholarly Monographs, from Technology to Usage”.
23. Open Science Conference 2019, Berlin, Germany, 19-20 March 2019, Andrea Bertino, Poster Presentation.
24. 7. Bibliothekskongress Leipzig 2019: “Bibliotheken verändern”, Leipzig, Germany, 18-21 March 2019, Margo Bargheer, Andrea Bertino, workshop: “Enhanced Publications – wie Forschungsbibliotheken innovative Publikationsformen unterstützen.”
25. Annual meeting AG Univerlage, Hamburg, 4-5 April 2019, Andrea Bertino, talk: “Univerlage, Infrastrukturen und die Zukunft der Monographie. Anstöße und Perspektiven aus der Erfahrung mit dem HIRMEOS”.
26. DARIAH-EU Annual Meeting, Warschau, Poland, 15-17 May 2019, Andrea Bertino: Poster Presentation.
27. HIRMEOS Workshop, “Shaping new Ways to Open the Book”, Marseille, France, 2 June 2019, All HIRMEOS WP Leaders, Presentations of the services.
28. ELPUB Conference, Marseille, France, 2-4 June 2019, Andrea Bertino, Rupert Gatti, Pierre Mounier, panel discussion: “Toward an Open Access Book Network”.
29. AEUP conference, Brno, Czech Republic, 12-14 June. Andrea Bertino, talk: “Festina lente – Developments and Mission of a University Press in the Context of an Infrastructural Project”; Pierre Mounier, talk: “From open access as a movement to open science as a policy (and why it is a challenge for us)”.
30. OAI 11 – The CERN-UNIGE Workshop on Innovations in Scholarly Communication, Geneva, Switzerland, 18-21 June 2019. Pierre Mounier, Talk: “Towards a European network to support open access monographs”.

General considerations

The participation in several conferences was initially aimed at raising awareness of the project's tasks and its specific implementations. In this initial phase we have therefore carried out **numerous poster presentations** at conferences and workshops on scholarly publishing

and digital humanities. This allowed us to come into contact with different communities. In general, we privileged posters that do not contain too much textual information in order to stimulate personal conversations during the poster presentation. Overall, these presentations proved to be very useful, also to clarify some misunderstandings about the nature of HIRMEOS, which was often identified as a new platform and not as a project. This erroneous conception is meaningful because it demonstrates that there is a general need for large and efficacious aggregators which, through appropriate forms of crosslinking, can connect monographs published on different platforms. In addition, a topic often discussed during these presentations was the non-commercial but open source nature of the different implementations. A large part of the interest in the project was due to the fact that each implementation can be easily used by other publishing platforms not involved in the project.

In a second phase, especially **presentations on specific project activities and implemented services** took place. Among the various talks on the different services, those on the metrics service and *entity-fishing* have received particular interest. At the ELPUB conference 2018 in Toronto, officers from Ubiquity Press explained the general structure of their HIRMEOS Working Group, exploring the different drivers, communication across the services and the principle of separation of concerns when dealing with altmetrics at the publisher level. They received good feedback, even if at that point in time the implementation of some components was still pending.

At the **PUBMET conference** 2018, Andrea Bertino showed how *entity-fishing* annotations can improve both the research and publishing process. On that occasion, book editors showed a particular interest in this service and the possibility of creating indexes in a semi-automatic way. Although the technical resources offered by NERD technologies are considered relevant by this category, they emphasize the importance of editorial work and the involvement of the book author in the realization of indexes.

In the last months there were presentations aimed at better reflecting the meaning of HIRMEOS in the broader context of the Open Science. Specifically, Pierre Mounier's key talk at the **AEUP conference** interpreted the possible further development of HIRMEOS in the context of OPERAS as manifestation of a more general process of institutionalisation of the various activities and projects related to OA scholarly publishing. At the same conference, Andrea Bertino stressed the possibility that local actors such as small non-profit university presses could have a decisive impact on the global system of scientific communication through participation in infrastructural projects.

In general, experience has shown that presentations were more successful where they were able to combine information about the project activities with some more general statements about the opportunities, challenges and prospects concerning scholarly communication and the role of OA Monographs in HSS. In this way, presentations help to develop broad narratives which may constitute a horizon of meaning useful to support new policies and concrete lines of action to support the publication in OA of scholarly books.

New Services and Tools for the Digital Monograph: the HIRMEOS Project
 Andrea C. Bertino, Göttingen State and University Library bertino@sub.uni-goettingen.de
 ELPUB - The 23rd International Conference on Electronic Publishing
 Academic Publishing and digital Bibliodiversity, June 02-04, 2019, Marseille, France

How to make the digital scholarly monograph fit for Open Access by applying smart services and tools

Annotation Service

A web-based annotation layer has been implemented on top of the publishing platforms. With the tool of *hypothes.is* users can annotate digital monographs in their own browser and save their annotations for themselves, for a defined private group or for the public.

Peer-Review Certification System

There is a prototype of a peer-review certification system in testing. Easy to understand icons display which kind of peer-review process has taken place to increase the confidence in the quality of the OA monographs published on the HIRMEOS partner platforms.

Identification Service

All documents published on the platforms are identified by Crossref DOIs. If an author has already an ORCID ID, the platforms involved in the project displays it next to their name. Through FundRef Data, it is now possible to identify the funding institution and the research project behind a specific publication.

Named Entity Recognition

The NERD service developed by INRIA and available within the DARIAH-EU infrastructure was used by the HIRMEOS partners to increase visibility and discoverability of digital monographs. One of the most implemented use cases was the improvement of the platform's search interface using entities extracted from the library content.

open access
scholarly
monograph

Metrics Service

The HIRMEOS platforms are concluding the implementation of a service enabling to collect data on views/downloads, Altmetrics, citations and annotations realized via *hypothes.is*. A web widget will allow to visualize usage, impact and resonance of a monograph by taking into account Google Books, OAPEN, OpenEdition, Unglue.it, JSTOR, Worldreader, OpenAire, IRUS-UK, Wikimedia.

HIRMEOS Main Goals

- Integrate Open Access monographs into the open science ecosystem in a systematic and coordinated fashion
- Prototype innovative services for monographs in support of Open Science infrastructure
- Provide additional data, links and interactions to the documents
- Boost user-driven innovation in the academic book publishing sector, both commercial and non-commercial
- Pave the way to new potential tools for research assessment

HIRMEOS Context

- HIRMEOS takes place within the larger network OPERAS (open access in the European research area through scholarly communication) that joins almost 30 partners to build a distributed research infrastructure for the Humanities and Social Sciences.
- The Project is run by nine European partners committed to innovative scholarly communication and is based upon five Open Access books publishing platforms giving access to more than 15000 scholarly books.

Stay updated about HIRMEOS activities by subscribing to our newsletter

www.hirmeos.eu

@hirmeos

hirmeos

1.2 Workshops organized

1. HIRMEOS Workshop: Valutazione della ricerca e servizi di identificazione/citazione: prospettive nelle scienze umane e sociali [Research evaluation and identifiers/citing services: perspectives in SSH] 21 March 2019, Turin (Italy).
2. HIRMEOS Workshop: Entity-Fishing for Digital Humanities and Scholarly Publishing, 4 September 2018, Göttingen (Germany).
3. HIRMEOS Workshop (with AEUP and Metopes): From Text to Structured Edition – Producing XML-TEI Content”, 11-13 December 2018, Göttingen (Germany).
4. HIRMEOS. Workshop: Open Annotation, 10 January 2019, Paris (France).
5. HIRMEOS Workshop: Metrics and Altmetrics for Open Access Monographs, 11 January 2019, Paris (France).
6. HIRMEOS Workshop: Shaping new ways to open the Book, 2 June 2019, Marseille (France).

General considerations

Workshops have been one of the most important parts of HIRMEOS communication activities. They allowed us to combine classic frontal presentations with moments of broad discussion: In all the workshops organized, we have favored a format that always combined these two formats, reserving broad space for final panel discussions. In addition, we have involved in these events representatives of different communities: IT developers, academics, librarians and publishers.

During The first **HIRMEOS Workshop in Turin** some common controversies, needs or concerns related to the usage of persistent identifiers were highlighted:

- scarce awareness on the benefit of identifiers like ORCID among researchers;
- one of the most needed identifiers turned out to be the funders' one;
- the lack of standards affects practices like citation counts;
- citation count can also be useful to draw and visualize research networks-common interest nodes;
- in SSH, attention should also be put on references and notes analysis as often citations could be context-sensitive; moreover, disciplinary differences must be taken into account as practices may vary a lot;
- more training concerning the use of persistent identifiers is needed both for authors and administrative supporting people.

The **workshop on *entity-fishing*** was essentially aimed at discussing some possible applications proposed by publishing service providers outside the HIRMEOS consortium. On the one hand, this allowed new use cases of the NERD technology to be critically tested together with the developers of entity-fishing. On the other hand, broader discussions developed about the present difficulties of the applications of these technologies in scholarly publishing. Ultimately, the overall impression is that the future use and realization of digital books will make intensive use of text mining techniques. However, in order to be really useful

and effective, it needs to develop and implement these technical resources through a continuous exchange between developers, publishers and readers. Research infrastructures are the best place to host and stimulate this exchange.

In cooperation with the projects Métopes and the Association of the European University Presses (AEUP) we organized our second **workshop ‘From Text to Structured Edition – Producing XML-TEI Content’**. This workshop, while giving space to a general presentation of the HIRMEOS Project, was not dedicated to any of the services implemented within the project. The event was aimed at editors and publishers who wanted to acquire knowledge and gain first-hand experience with tools for creating standardized documents in XML. The choice of this topic was motivated by the fact that many text mining techniques, as well as many recommendations from OA policies such as PlanS, make it urgent for many publishers to be able to publish formats other than PDF as well. This workshop also confirmed another important aspect of communication activities related to technical innovations for OA publishing: a holistic approach is required. The different services cannot be considered in their isolation but as related parts of complex system. This also applies for example to annotation and metrics services, or to the identification service and all other services implemented. Such an approach requires, however, a network of different specialists providing information and support in a coordinated and synergistic way.

The **workshop ‘Why does Open Annotation matter?’** focused on possible applications of the annotation tool in scholarly research and teaching, scientific blogging and open peer review. Remarks and comments, when made public, can be considered an indicator of resonance, influence and impact. Therefore, any service aimed at a bibliometric analysis of scholarly production must also pay attention to text annotations. To this aim, the HIRMEOS Project implemented an online annotation tool, *hypothes.is* on its publishing platforms and the WP5 and WP7 tried to push its use. The workshop started with considerations on the cultural-historical aspects of annotating texts with Christian Jacob from EHESS. Afterwards, the *hypothes.is* tool for annotation of digital documents was presented by Heather Staines from *hypothes.is*. Implementation and use on the digital platforms involved in the HIRMEOS project was then presented by Hirmeos officers. Three specific usage scenarios in context outsider the HIRMEOS consortium were then presented by invited speakers: open education (Micah Vandergrift), scientific blogging (Mareike König), open peer review (Edit Gorogh). Discussion on those specific scenarios were then held to allow participants to get some practical experiences with the annotation of digital texts. General recommendations for the use of the annotation tool on digital monographs and other forms of texts were formulated at the end of the project.

The **workshop ‘Metrics and Altmetrics for Open Access Monographs’** was focussing on the HIRMEOS service aimed at collecting and visualizing metrics and altmetric data for OA monographs in HSS. The first part of this workshop was dedicated to presenting the implementation on the digital platforms involved in the HIRMEOS project and the technical challenges that were involved. The second part was dedicated to the presentation of the use of metrics in national evaluation cultures (in France (Didier Torny), within ENRESSH infrastructure (Iona Galleron), and Italy (Elena Giglia)). Afterwards, together with scholars

from HSS, digital platform providers, members of funding institutions and librarians, we considered the impact of metrics on scholarly publishers, research organisations and libraries, above all discussing in which way metrics tools can contribute to an informed decision-making in research evaluation and library management (s. Hirmeos Deliverable 6.3 “Minutes of the workshop on new book metrics”).

The **final HIRMEOS workshop ‘Shaping new Ways to Open the Book’**, organized in the context of the 23rd ELPUB Conference, was dedicated to sustainability and future perspectives in scholarly monograph publishing. After Lucy Montgomery’s keynote *Don’t talk to me about metrics! I write books!*, we discussed how the HIRMEOS services enable and incentivize innovative scholarly practices and how such practices could be better integrated into everyday scholarly, librarian and publishing workflows. In the second half of the day, we invited early-career researchers to jointly outline future perspectives and the next steps in the development of open scholarly monographs.

In the course of the workshop, crucial issues concerning the publication in OA of scholarly monographs as well as the acceptance of the OS paradigm in the field of HSS were addressed several times. Thanks to a lively exchange between participants from different communities, some general **recommendations** were pointed out. These should be taken into account in future actions of research infrastructures which, like OPERAS, intend to support the integration of HSS disciplines into the OS system.

- The current tenure and promotion criteria is recognized as a major impediment for innovations in OA monograph publishing. *Increasing transparency in peer-review and sensible implementing of book usage metrics can contribute to enriching the evaluation culture by situating the assessment of quality and resonance in a broader context than the traditional prestige economy.*
- It is not always easy for scholars and librarians to keep track of the increasingly diverse and complex routes that a book can take on its journey from writer to reader. *Community-driven services or registries should contribute to develop a dynamic overview of these.*
- *Scholars should be better involved in the book publication process and be more informed of choices about the dissemination strategies for their work.* To this aim different initiatives are possible, e.g. supporting collaboration between research groups and academic publishers through some kind of *OA Book network*, participating in the *Radical Open Access Collective* or developing some kind of *OA Book navigator service*.

Fig. 2: Final workshop: overall satisfaction

Fig. 3: Final workshop: Relevance of content

Fig. 4: Final workshop: participant types

1.3 Webinars

- Entity-fishing for scholarly monographs, 5 March 2018.
- A peer-review certification system for OA Books, 24 June 2019.

General considerations

The webinar is a simple and effective tool to disseminate information about project activities and collect feedback from different communities. In the course of the HIRMEOS Project, two webinars were organised, one on the NERD service and the other on the peer-review certification system. In the former, representatives of publishing platforms and IT-Officers presented different aspects of the development of publishing services on the basis of the *entity-fishing* tool. In the latter, we have shown why the HIRMEOS certification system is of great importance for early-careers researchers, university publishers and librarians. Both webinars have been recorded and made available on the HIRMEOS website.

1.4 Peer-reviewed Papers

1. Bertino A., Staines H.: Enabling a Conversation across Scholarly Monographs through Open Annotation, in: *Publications 2019*, 7(2) special Issue *New Frontiers for Openness in Scholarly Publishing*, 41; <https://doi.org/10.3390/publications7020041>.
2. Bertino A.; Foppiano L.; Mounier P.; Romary L.: Leveraging Concepts in Open Access Publications, in: *Journal of Data Mining and Digital Humanities* (peer-review passed) 2019.
3. Bargheer, M. Bertino A.: HIRMEOS. Ein EU-Projekt für Open Access-Monographien in den Geistes- und Sozialwissenschaften, in: *Bibliothek Forschung und Praxis* 42.3 (2018) .

4. Schmidt, B.; Bertino, A.; Beucke, D.; Brinken, H.; Jahn, N.; Matthias, L.; Mimkes, J.; Müller, K.; Orth, A.; Bargheer, M.: Open Science Support as a Portfolio of Services and Projects: From Awareness to Engagement, in: Publications 2018, 6, 27.
5. Bargheer, M., Dogan, Z. M., Horstmann, W., Mertens, M. and Rapp, A., 2017. Unlocking the digital potential of scholarly monographs in 21st century research. LIBER Quarterly, 27(1), pp.194–211. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.18352/lq.1017>.
6. Ernst, E.,: The Value of Network Sustainability. Why we Join Research Infrastructures, in: Connecting the Knowledge Common. From Projects to Sustainable Infrastructures, edited by Leslie Chan, Pierre Mounier 2019, pp. 77-96.
7. Arias, J.,: Collecting Inclusive Usage Metrics for Open Access Publications: the HIRMEOS Project. 2018. In Proceedings of the 22nd International Conference on Electronic Publishing. Toronto, Canada: Open Edition. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.4000/proceedings.elpub.2018.11>

General considerations

Publications (3),(4) and (5) presented general aspects of the HIRMEOS Project or of the situation of the digital monograph in today's publishing landscape. These three contributions have been peer-reviewed and published in internationally prestigious journals. Publications (6) and (7) ran through a peer-review process and were published accompanied to the international conference ELPUB for electronic publishing; while (6) considers the connection to OPERAS and the benefit for small organisations to involve themselves in these types of projects, (7) argues how the metrics service has been designed to work for all sort of organisations, therefore emphasising its inclusivity.

Papers (1) and (2) are official deliverables of our project (D 7.3 *One research publication on NERD and enabling new forms of academic publication* and D 7.4 *Research Publication on the annotation tool*) and were also published after peer review.

The paper (2) addresses the integration of the Named Entity Recognition and Disambiguation (NERD) service within OA publishing platforms and considers its potential impact on both research and scholarly publishing. In the paper, we focus on the specific issues related to its integration on the five platforms participating in HIRMEOS and we show that *entity-fishing* annotations can improve both research and publishing process. Also concerning other service implemented in the course of the project, paper (7) presents the contribution of Open Book Publishers to create and populate, in the framework of HIRMEOS, a database of title-specific usage data with metrics across multiple different platforms and formats, normalised in a standard that allows clear identification of the meaning of these numbers and their origin

Concrete examples and recommendations for exploiting the potential of mass annotation in academic research and teaching are discussed in the paper (1). After presenting the open annotation tool of Hypothesis, the article focuses on its use in the context of HIRMEOS. The general line and the aims of the post-peer review experiment lead by OpenEdition, as well as its usage in didactic activities concerning monographic publications lead by SUB

Göttingen were presented and proposed as potential best practices for similar annotation activities.

Basing upon the findings of the *OPERAS Design Study* the paper (6) presents the concept of network sustainability and thus offers a good conceptual basis for the development of infrastructure cooperation initiatives which, as in the specific case of an OA book network, could contribute significantly to the realization and acceptance of the OA scholarly monograph.

1.5 Other Publications

1. Bertino A.; Foppiano L; Arias J.; Ekanger A.; Thoden K.: Entity-fishing for Scholarly Publishing: Challenges and Recommendations. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1476475
2. E. Heinemann; A. Bertino; F. Di Donato; A. Ekanger; E. Giglia; B. Jędraszko; M. Kaiser; L. Matthias; A. Smaniotto: OPERAS Advocacy White Paper, July 30, 2018. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1324036
3. Bertino, Andrea C., Bargheer, Margo, & Meinecke, Isabella. (2018). Open Access und Monographien. Eine Begriffslandkarte. Zenodo. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1299192>

Fig. 5: Conceptual map realized for the hands-on lab at the German Librarian Days 2018

1.6 Fact-sheets

1. *Entity-fishing* for scholarly monographs
2. Annotation service for digital monographs

General Considerations

The aim of the factsheets was to present, both in digital and printed format, use cases and recommendations for some of the implemented services. This was essential for the **NERD tool** and the annotation service, whose possible applications are still to be fully explored and need exemplification of use cases and guidelines. In the first case, the use cases described were intended to help publishing service providers assess the impact which text mining services based on this technology can have on consolidated workflows and the organization of editorial processes. In the case of the **annotation service**, two practices were highlighted – open annotation for post-peer-review and annotation for educational purposes – whose uptake by many academic communities is still very low.

Annotation Service for Digital Monographs

Why Open Annotation

Open Annotation is essential in nearly any part of the research lifecycle. It enables organization and collaboration atop research materials; inline peer review; augmentation of articles with additional information, links, images or videos; elaboration around citations; content corrections or updates, and has extensive use cases in the teaching and learning space

The Hypothes.is Tool

The Hypothes.is Annotation Tool allows annotations at a sentence or phrase level, such as criticism or notes on news, blogs, scientific articles, books, terms of use, campaign initiatives, legislative procedures, and more. The tool is based on an open source JavaScript library and annotation standards developed by the World Wide Web Consortia (W3C)

The Implementation of the Tool

The publishing platforms participating in HIRMEOS were provided with JavaScript libraries, which they embedded in their websites, to create annotations around the HTML, ePub and PDF version of the monographs so that users are not required to install the Hypothes.is plug-in on their browsers when reading the books published on the platform

Support to Academic Community Engagement

Post-publication Open Peer Review by OpenEdition Books

- 13 books from 4 publishers opened for annotation
- Creation of a space both for scientific conversation and new forms of peer review
- Annotators were supported in learning to use Hypothes.is
- Annotations will be the subject of a report

Annotation Activities in Seminar coordinated by SUB Göttingen

- Interpretation of a classic of philosophy
- Improving students' preparation and follow-up of the individual sessions
- Deeper understanding of the discussed texts
- More efficient way for lecturers to communicate with students and between the students
- Streamlined management of the students' homework

More Information

Do you want to know more about Annotation Services and HIRMEOS support to the usage of the hypothesis tool? Visit www.hirmeos.eu and subscribe to our newsletter

1.7 Other Dissemination Materials

- 2 Flyers
- 1 Postcard
- Different Stickers

Fig. 7: One of the flyers developed at the beginning of the project

1.8 Video & Hypervideo

The HIRMEOS project <https://vimeo.com/260765668>

General considerations

The video was particularly useful for presenting the project quickly and vividly on various occasions like lightning talks at conferences, individual meetings, webinars, etc.

Together with the dissemination of the video, an attempt was made to integrate into the HIRMEOS website a hypervideo presenting the same video together with a series of external links to textual documents or other kinds of resources on the topic of the OA digital monograph. This attempt was only partially successful, as the specific open source technology used to realize the hypervideo does not yet allow excellent visualization. However, this experiment remains relevant as a general idea to realize a crowdsourcing

system aimed at filling a public bibliography on the topic of the OA monograph that may be continued after the project is completed, perhaps in the context of an Open Access book network.

1.9 Website and Social Networks

Relevant Numbers (1 April 2017- 28 June 2019)

Website sessions	8901
Website page views	17411
Blog Posts	49
Twitter Followers	718
Twitters	1337
Twitter Impressions	565900
Newsletter	7

Website

Our website has played a key role in our communication strategy, being the core of the HIRMEOS identity and providing information about the project activities and the realized deliverables. Its contact form has enabled 103 visitors to register for the HIRMEOS mailing list.

Fig. 8: HIRMEOS website analytics (April 2017-June 2019)

Fig 9: HIRMEOS website visitors: most represented countries

Social Networks

At the beginning of the project, communication channels on Google+, Facebook and Twitter were activated. Over time, the primary importance of Twitter for our community outreach has become apparent and we have therefore focused our social networking on this medium. Twitter was used both to present the publication of new results and to promote participation in the events we organized, to make the activities of the project partners visible and to inform about initiatives, publications, conferences, etc. that are of interest for the topic of the digital monograph.

28 day summary with change over previous period

Fig. 10: Twitter last 28 days (28 June 2019)

Fig. 11: Twitter Impressions from April 2017 to 28 June 2019

Fig. 12: A tweet on our last webinar

PART 2: Strengthening the OA Book in different Communities

2.1 Academic Communities

2.1.1 Context of the Communication Activities

A generic advocacy in favor of the use and production of OA books seems to be destined to remain ineffective until an added value is created for this form of scholarly communication. In fact, the mere prospect of better dissemination through OA is thwarted by the priority of most scholars to remain visible to specific scientific communities using well-established communication channels – i.e. traditional publishers not publishing in OA – which are also likely to better ensure the recognition of the scientific quality of their publications.

In addition to concerns about the recognition of the quality of OA monographs, the impact of metrics on research evaluation is also problematic. Together these have been identified as two of the main obstacles of the dissemination of this type of publication.

The availability of tools for open annotation was often unknown or not clearly perceived by many scholars and publishers as an opportunity to increase interaction with digital monographs.

2.1.2 Results and Perspectives

Faced with these concerns, the HIRMEOS WP 7 has first tried to show, both through conference presentations and face-to-face meetings, how publishing platforms can assure the recognition of scientific quality by certifying the peer review processes.

Then, during the **HIRMEOS Workshop on “Metrics and Altmetrics for Open Access Monograph”** organized in Paris, we placed particular emphasis on the need to develop metrics services according to the needs of the specific scholarly communities in the HSS. Also during our final workshop ‘Shaping new ways to open the Book’ in Marseille, we have highlighted the following aspects and presented them to of many early-career researchers in HSS:

- The development of metrics should not be interpreted as an attempt to reduce the scientific quality of publications to their impact by reproducing some perversions that have characterized the use of the impact factor in STEM disciplines.
- The visualization of bibliometric data and altmetrics must not lead to a ‘gamification’ of the research activity. It is necessary to avoid an indistinct merging of different kinds of metrics data by presenting them in a single indicator supposed to represent use and/or resonance of a specific publication. Rather, preference must be given to dashboards and widgets that can present all different types of captured data clearly

and transparently, so that the user can then interpret the value of that data in the best way.

As for the use of open annotation tools – also a specific object of an **experiment of open peer-review in WP 5** (s. Deliverable 5.3 *Report on post-publication open peer review experiment*) – we have focused the activities of WP7 on a discipline particularly reluctant to publish in OA and use innovative tools, namely *philosophy*. The Göttingen university library supported lecturers and students at the University of Göttingen in **annotating through the *hypothesis*.is tool a monograph interpreted in a philosophy seminar**. Lecturers used the tool to facilitate the preparation and follow-up of the individual seminar meetings, each of which deals with a specific part of the discussed book.

By the time this report was drawn up, the activity had not yet been completed, but after less than two months almost 100 annotations had been made. The experiment has a meaning that goes beyond the mere fostering of the use of Open Annotation tools for digital monographs:

- By emphasizing the need that a monograph, in order to be public annotable, must be published in OA, the activity helped to spread the message that research and teaching need OA resources in order to use innovative tools. This is in line with the general idea that inspires our communication strategy, according to which the best form of advocacy is through concrete technical incentives and direct involvement of communities in the use of new tools.
- This practice has supported the production of a considerable amount of so-called grey literature. Some highly articulated and well-formulated annotations may be of interest to other students outside the specific course involved in the experiment. This helps to draw the attention of students, scholars and publishers to new forms of OA publications. Considering this specific case, it is conceivable that in the near future forms of enhanced monographs, like annotated seminar readers, may be realized.
- The experiment draws attention to the essential role of research libraries. They can play a crucial role in the introduction of new tools for digital publications in three ways:
 - ❖ by supporting training in the use of these tools;
 - ❖ by providing appropriate repositories for the long-term preservation of texts and annotations;
 - ❖ by providing publishing services for the realization of enhanced publications based on primary literature and user annotations.

Philosophy has also been at the centre of general efforts to promote the benefits of OA publishing. As part of these activities, we have tried to involve several scholars directly in editorial projects, and finally we were able to start an **OA book project** with a german author:

Werner Stegmaier, *Europa im Geisterkrieg. Studien zu Nietzsche*, eds. by A. Bertino, Cambridge (Open Books Publisher) 2019, DOI: 10.11647/OBP.0133.

Beyond its scientific value, this publication can represent an exemplary case for an entire discipline, not only in German-speaking countries, for at least two reasons

- The author of this book has a consolidated scientific profile but this book is his first OA publication. He works in a research field where there is practically no relevant OA scientific literature. Also the endorsements published on the book come from established scholars who have never published in OA.
- The publication was realized in cooperation between a German author and an English publisher, and under the coordination of the HIRMEOS Officer. The decision due to the lack of a university press or a publishing service at the author’s university has once again demonstrated the importance of infrastructural solutions in the absence of suitable publication models at national level.

About a year after its publication, the monograph, albeit in German and very subject-specific, was consulted more than 1500 times, from different countries.

Metrics report - Europa im Geisterkrieg. Studien zu Nietzsche			
Online Readership ?			
Platform	2018	2019	Totals
OBP HTML Reader	141	52	193
OBP PDF Reader	208	121	329
Open Edition		97	97
Google Books	296	409	705
Total Online Reader	645	679	1324

Fig. 13: OA Book realized with OBP: Online readership

Readership graphs - Europa im Geisterkrieg. Studien zu Nietzsche

Unique Visits to Online Readers by Country
(when available)

Unique Visits to Online Readers by Continent
(when available)

* 'Other' represents the remaining countries from which we have received visits. The number of visits from each country is too small to list individually

Fig 14: OA Book realized with OBP: Unique visits by country

2.2 University Presses and Libraries

2.2.1 Context of the Communication Activities

University presses as well as university libraries providing archiving and publishing services play a key role in integrating monographs into the OS landscape. Although they often primarily serve a restricted local community, by participating in infrastructural projects they can have an impact on the entire scientific publishing system by supporting the implementation of new services. It is precisely their non-profit character that allows them to experiment, with a certain freedom, the use of various tools whose impact on the scholarly community and editorial work is not yet clear.

2.2.2 Results and Perspectives

During the project, we reach several publishing service providers outside the project. Especially during the implementation of the entity recognition Service, we were able to involve in the test of new use cases *Edition Open Access*, the publishing service of the Max Planck Research Library for the History and Development of Knowledge, and *Septentrio Academic Publishing*, the publishing service provided by the University Library of Tromsø. In addition, the **AG Univerlage working group**, which brings together many German-speaking university presses, have taken up our activities with interest, hosting some of our

presentations and facilitating individual exchanges about the various services implemented by HIRMEOS, in particular the peer-review certification system and the metrics service.

Also with the **Association of the European University Press (AEUP)** we cooperated very intensively. With more than 40 members from many European countries, AEUP represents an extremely important network for the activities of HIRMEOS. Our consortium organised together with AEUP a workshop on XML offering hands-on experience with Métopes software. The participants of the workshop had been asked to bring documents with various kinds of content to experiment on. They learned the basic steps, such as organizing files and folders and navigating the Métopes software, proceeding to more specific requirements of formatting. After tackling the issue of exporting the prepared file to XML format, different export formats from XML were discussed and practiced (epub, InDesign files etc.). The practical part included work on different data levels (chapter, article, whole book) and content elements (tables, pictures etc). As many publishers work with Adobe InDesign, the last day of the workshop was largely devoted to specific issues of importing XML to InDesign. The feedback from the participants of the workshop was very positive. Many suggestions were made regarding specific requirements of the publishers (such as integration with OJS), and future cooperation with Métopes was regarded as highly fruitful. The role of AEUP in this cooperation is best described as an intermediary and an aggregator of ideas.

At the 7th German Librarians Congress in Berlin, we critically discussed the relevance of **enhanced publications and the role of research libraries** in their realisation. In fact, today digital platforms for education or research can support research and teaching, paving the way for innovative publication formats. However, collaboratively created results on platforms do not automatically become publications that are fully accepted and subsequently used in their respective disciplines. In our hands-on lab we have worked out which prerequisites research libraries could create in order to turn these results into citable, extended publications. In particular, we focused on enhanced publication resulting from the interaction of several people through virtual research environments, such as handbooks, readers, anthologies, editions, etc. The following aspects were particularly focused on: Integration of additional material (images, data, etc.); Versioning / citation information; Standard formats for further processing and re-use; Persistent identifier for interoperability and proof of use; quality assurance; Long-term availability of publications.

The HIRMEOS hand-on lab helped to address the key challenges that need to be considered when designing new services for enhanced publications:

- If innovative forms of publication are based on modular media types or technologies, sustainability must exist for individual components and vertical integration.
- Enhanced publications often contain complex legal and licensing relationships, which influence technology and consulting.
- Publications must remain reliably citable for many years: Service development thus has a "long tail".
- Disciplinary expectations of innovative forms of publication, such as quality assurance, branding, or scientific traceability

2.3 Funding Institutions

2.3.1 Context of the Communication Activities

Funding Institutions can make a significant contribution to the acceptance of OA monographs by formulating policies requiring the OA dissemination of publicly funded research projects. The development of such policies goes beyond the aims of the HIRMEOS project. However, during the course of the project, we had several opportunities to highlight the importance of the contribution of funding institutions to maximize the impact of the technical solutions developed by our consortium.

2.3.2 Results and Perspectives

At the **workshop ‘Die Zukunft des wissenschaftlichen Buches: Monographien in Open Access’** (engl. ‘The Future of Scientific Books: Monographs in Open Access’ organized by the Allianz der Wissenschaftsorganisationen in Bonn, we presented the HIRMEOS project and in particular its contribution to ensuring the scientific quality of OA publications and to the development of appropriate metrics services - issues of particular importance to funding institutions. During this event we had the opportunity to draw the attention of delegates of the German Research Council (DFG) to their possible contribution to an efficacious implementation of identification services. For example, the German Research Council and other national funding institutions could make a significant contribution to better identification of authors by requiring, as already in many European countries, the creation of an ORCID account by researchers applying for funding. This would make it possible to improve not only to the cross-linking of OA books, but also to the implementation of metric services, which always rely on the identifiability of authors and publications. With the work done by the WP2 for identification Service, HIRMEOS has created the technical basis for the visualization of persistent identifiers on the publishing platforms involved in the project. Now, appropriate policies must explicitly support the implementation of good scientific and editorial practice.

The partner organization **DARIAH-EU** acted as a connector between the diverse research communities in arts and humanities and key policy bodies such as the Open Science Policy Platform. In 2018 and 2019, DARIAH participated in a range of high-level consultations about scholarly communication. During these consultations and briefings DARIAH officers find especially important to raise funders’ and policy-makers’ awareness to the innovation that HIRMEOS was realizing. For instance, in our [statement on Plan S](#), we argue for increased support for developments of this kind and suggest to complement Plan S by a 5-year open monograph strategy that is flexible enough to stay compliant with the different national policies.

Joining forces and actively collaborate with complementary organizations like OPERAS or the European Alliance for Social Sciences and Humanities (EASSH) enables us to act as a critical mass in creating a sustainable environment for Open Access monographs and optimizing the research environment for the long-term good of our communities.

Abbreviations

HSS	Humanities and Social Sciences
OA	Open Access
OS	Open Science
RI	Research Infrastructure
WP	Work Package